

VIRTUAL REALITY AS A NEW METHOD OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7112404>

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Abstract: *Pedagogy is enriched with new types of training sessions, which are possible with the development of virtual reality technology. The usual trappings in distance learning and blended learning are complemented by interactive audio-video online sessions. As theoretical methods become more thoroughly explored, there is an increasing need to experiment with practical ones. Now we can see what role VR will play in the field of foreign language learning in the future. An analysis of the definition of the concept of virtuality made it possible to identify its main features and capabilities, allowing us to speak of virtual reality as an ideal educational environment.*

Keywords: *virtual reality, education, foreign languages, virtual reality technologies.*

INTRODUCTION

The study of the mechanisms of language and speech abilities of the processes of speech perception and speech generation showed that the most effective method of teaching a foreign language is the method of complete immersion, since students enter the natural language environment and are constantly in it. Since the possibility of living and studying abroad, for the majority of foreign language learners, is not generally available, methodologists and teachers are constantly looking for alternative teaching methods and creating educational models close to the natural language environment. This includes both short-term language courses abroad, bilingual education, international academic mobility projects, and active learning methods, such as business games, video, immersion, case studies, etc.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

It should be noted that the learning process in the classroom, no matter how organized and communicative, cannot replace the experience of real language learning. Scientists note that the study of a foreign language in textbooks and in the classroom as a whole limits the progress in mastering and using the language, which is especially noticeable in such areas as teaching vocabulary, speech rate, spontaneous speech and intercultural competencies.

These shortcomings emphasize, on the one hand, the importance of the language environment for effective learning, and on the other hand, the leading role of motivation in language learning. Accordingly, the development of new motivational environments for language learning, including virtual reality, is the main and necessary element of the learning process. The development of virtual reality technologies makes it possible to expand the boundaries of science and introduce innovations into all spheres of human activity.

In schools in the USA, China and Japan, such virtual technologies and virtual environments are already widely used, and virtual lessons are in full swing in Uzbekistan, augmented and virtual reality technologies are used only in some schools and universities.

This is not yet included in the compulsory education program. The concept of virtual reality is used to refer to three-dimensional computer macromodels. It rapidly expanded its terminological boundaries, becoming one of the universal characteristics of information activity.

After analyzing the definitions of the concept of virtuality proposed by various researchers, one can single out its main features - the relevance of virtual objects exists only actually here.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In pedagogy, virtual reality is mainly used as a special information space where a student can receive certain information, make contacts, elements of scientific, educational and project activities.

Virtual reality radically transforms the principle of visualization by creating a semblance of real objects through information modeling. As a result, the student gets almost the same or stronger personal experience in visual auditory tactile olfactory perception in the implementation of actions as in real interaction with similar situations. Virtual reality is one of the pinnacles of computerized learning. It achieves overstimulation of the senses,

similar to obtaining real perceptual experience, which is the basis of learning, including intellectual learning.

A foreign language teacher using virtual reality can create real situational interaction, such as an interview when applying for a job situation in a restaurant at an airport, etc. Virtual space can vary depending on the goals of the language level, the time frame, the number of participants, the real or animated characters used devices, etc. The use of virtual reality helps to overcome many of the difficulties of traditional learning.

Why do 95% of people fail when learning a foreign language?

According to statistics, about 1 billion people study English, and for such a sample, the figure of 95% is a huge loss.

In a study conducted in 2010, Professor of Linguistics, Carmen Munoz, identified the main reasons that hinder rapid and successful language learning:

1. Classes are limited to 2-4 sessions per week for 50 minutes per session.
2. The target language is not a language commonly used between peers.
3. The target language is often not used outside of the class.

The factor that unites these 3 reasons is the lack of immersion in the natural environment of using the language. In this regard, the emergence of AR and VR provides great opportunities.

Constant linguistic interaction with the society is the optimal environment for the successful learning of a foreign language. VR and AR can solve this problem.

At the moment, the market for educational products for learning languages in virtual reality is small. The list of scientific studies on this topic is limited to a small number of publications. Nevertheless, all scientific publications talk about the advantages of a virtual educational environment, such as visibility, involvement, focus, the effect of presence, overstimulation of the senses, safety, and many others.

For example, there is a specialized program called MondlyVR - an application specifically for learning languages. The student is "transferred" to a virtual environment where they can interact with virtual characters using speech recognition technology. Immediately after starting the program, the student indicates his native language and chooses one of thirty languages for learning. The user can then choose in which situations they want to practice their communication skills: train, taxi, hotel reception, and restaurant. Students also take lexical mini-lessons on topics such as animals, vegetables, fruits, space.

CONCLUSION

The market for learning foreign languages in virtual reality is a lot of disparate developments of varying degrees of quality and completeness. Unlike the market for English textbooks, which has its own leaders and canons developed in the course of numerous studies, there are no such leaders in the field of virtual reality. It is important to remember that foreign language teaching techniques in virtual reality are one of the tools that complement the existing set of methodological tools. Its effectiveness in comparison with other methods of remote language

learning (Skype, mobile applications, online courses) has yet to be proven. And despite all the advantages and potential of VR, the use of technology should be reasonable and consistent with the principle of didactic expediency - new technologies should be used only in those educational situations where traditional methods are less effective. Modern language programs for general language training are not limited to exercises and texts from textbooks: the teacher tries to use audio, video, presentations, games, speaking cards, cases, online platforms, mobile applications and so on in his lessons, the list of tools is quite wide. We hope that virtual reality will become one of the available methods for learning foreign languages.

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